

THE ROLE OF SELF-REFLECTION AND PEER-FEEDBACK IN DEVELOPING SOCIOCULTURAL COMPETENCE AMONG PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS

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***Abstract.** In many countries of the world, self-assessment (internal assessment) of schools has been introduced as a component of the educational quality assessment system. The practical application of the concept of self-assessment presupposes a conceptual and methodological understanding of the quality of education and implies a number of tools that can be adapted to different contexts and realities. The system of internal evaluation of schools implemented in Armenia is multifaceted and complex in many ways. It differs from the assessment mechanisms and tools adopted in many countries. The qualitative and quantitative indicators developed in Armenia are designed to reflect the rapidly evolving context and socio-economic changes affecting the educational process.*

***Keywords.** Education system, social changes, quality of education, secondary school, self-assessment, methodology, school effectiveness, indicators.*

Introduction. The function of education is to transfer cultural values and scientific achievements from generation to generation, which contributes to adaptation to new realities and situations. In recent years, social, socio-economic and political processes have decisively begun to influence the education process as a whole. Ensuring the required quality of the educational system (schools and universities) can be achieved only through effective management and an objective assessment of the functioning and development of all elements of the educational system. Effective management of educational activities, in turn, is impossible without a continuous flow of information, its quantitative and qualitative analysis, self-analysis of the professional activities of participants in education, monitoring,

modernization and optimization based on the results obtained.

Main Part. The concept of "quality of education" implies the following components:

- students who are ready to learn and have support in their families;
- an educational environment that is well-maintained, favorable and safe, provided with the necessary conditions and resources;
- the content of education, which is determined by state standards, subject programs, curricula and relevant educational materials, which ensures that students develop the necessary general cultural and educational competencies;
- qualified teaching staff that provides a person-centered approach to the learning process;
- professional management of educational institutions;
- objective assessment that motivates students' learning and cognitive interests and reduces the threshold of distrust;
- Learning outcomes that include knowledge.

Peer and self-assessment are important components of assessment for learning. As stated in the famous pamphlet 'Assessment for Learning: Beyond the Black Box' (Assessment Reform Group 1999), the need for students to be able to self-assess and understand how to improve their own learning is critical for enhancing learning through assessment. In self-assessment, students evaluate their own work, based on well-understood criteria or standards so as to improve their learning and performance (Brown and Harris 2013). This involves a variety of techniques 'through which students describe (i.e., assess) and possibly assign merit or worth to (i.e., evaluate) the qualities of their own learning processes and products'.

Conclusion. Thus, the "Methodological guide for the internal assessment of the activities of a general education institution" developed by us, which differs in many ways from the assessment tools adopted in many countries in its versatility and complexity, is designed to form a unified conceptual and methodological

understanding of the quality of education in general education schools of the Republic Armenia, as well as to offer standardized tools for its measurements using unified approaches to collect and analyze the necessary information. The positive experience of using the Armenian model can be used by other countries.

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ENHANCING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE THROUGH TASK-BASED LEARNING IN MIDDLE SCHOOL

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***Abstract.** This article discusses the theoretical foundations of TBL, its impact on language learning, and practical applications within middle school education. The conclusion emphasizes how TBL supports both linguistic and social skills development, ultimately fostering more confident communicators. Also, the role of task-based learning (TBL) in promoting communicative*